

Full Length Article

Morphology-dependent near-infrared photothermal activity of plasmonic TiN nanobars and nanospheres for anticancer, antibacterial therapy and deep *in vivo* photoacoustic imaging

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ABSTRACT

Plasmonic titanium nitride (TiN) nanoparticles are emerging nanomaterials possessing several orders of magnitude higher absorption cross section, but also exhibit higher photostability compared to conventional photosensitizers. In the recent years, TiN has emerged as a highly effective electrocatalytic and environmentally friendly material with good biocompatibility. Its unique physicochemical properties and cost-effectiveness are essential for wide utilization in biomedicine. However, the effect of morphology of TiN on the photothermal therapy (PTT) efficiency has not been studied yet. Here, TiN nanocrystals of two precisely defined morphologies - nanobars and nanospheres - were prepared by unique pseudomorphic conversion of TiO₂ nanowires and nanospheres via nitridation at 800 °C. Due to their multiple plasmonic resonances, the resulting materials show broad optical absorption spanning the entire solar spectrum and biological window including the NIR-I (750 – 1000 nm) and NIR-II (1000 – 1350 nm). Using low power illumination 318 mW/cm² and NIR LED irradiation 940 nm, we observed a morphology-dependent PTT bioactivity, with the TiN nanobars being more efficient in cancer HeLa cells killing, while nanospheres showed higher antimicrobial activity toward *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* bacteria strains. Moreover, acute and long-term *in vitro* biocompatibility together with *in vivo* monitoring of biodistribution showing enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect were confirmed by photoacoustic (PA) imaging in tumor bearing mice (C57BL/6J albino, EL4 lymphoma cell line). Thus, both TiN morphologies - nanobars and nanospheres are promising candidates in theranostic application via PTT therapy and PA imaging.

1. Introduction

Plasmonic nanomaterials exhibit strong light-matter interaction thanks to the collective oscillation of their surface free electrons, forming what is known as localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR)

[1,2]. As compared to conventional photosensitizers (e.g. molecular dyes and semiconductors), plasmonic nanomaterials not only possess several orders of magnitude higher absorption cross section, but also exhibit higher photostability [2]. Plasmonic nanostructures allow to concentrate light in nanoscale volumes producing intense near fields.

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Consequently, this phenomenon enables strong enhancement of both chemical and physical effects essential for nonlinear optical sensors [3], thermal conduction [4,5], and chemical reactions [6–8] among others. After plasmon excitation decay, the stored energy is dissipated through the formation of hot carriers that eventually produce lattice thermalization and significant local heating [9]. These properties have sparked interest in nanobiotechnologies. The strong plasmon absorption and photothermal conversion have been extensively investigated for noble metals such as Au, Ag, Pt, and Pd nanostructures [10–17]. Major research efforts have been focused on plasmonic nanoparticles with LSPR in the NIR spectral range for the photothermal based cancer treatment over the past decades [18,19]. Besides the use of high thermal efficiency of plasmonic materials for cancer therapy, they are also attractive in other applications in biomedicine, such as drug delivery to maximize therapeutic efficacy by transporting and releasing the drug, in biosensing, as implants [20–24] and imaging of chemical and biological agents [25]. However, the potential of plasmonic semimetallic materials, mainly TiN, generating intense local heating for effective anticancer photothermal therapy is less explored and for the purpose of antibacterial treatment has not been studied yet.

In the recent years, TiN has emerged as a highly effective electrocatalytic and environmental friendly material with good biocompatibility. Its unique physicochemical properties, such as low electrical resistance, outstanding chemical stability, high electronic conductivity, and cost-effectiveness are essential for wide utilization in surgical tools, implants and food-contact applications [26,27]. TiN semi-metals are inexpensive compared with the noble metals, more efficient, stable and less toxic than other studied plasmonic materials [28–35]. Furthermore, TiN nanostructures exhibit an excellent thermal stability up to 1400 °C [36–38]. Distinct from spherical gold nanoparticles having diameter of tens of nanometers, which have their absorption band (520 – 600 nm) outside the biological transparency window (630 – 900 nm), the localized surface plasmon resonance of TiN NPs is just located within the biological transparency window where high absorption efficiencies can be obtained using similar dimensions than Au counterpart [39,40].

TiN nanocrystals showing surface plasmon resonance in the NIR range can serve not only as PTT therapeutic agent in mild conditions but they can be also utilized as contrast agent in photoacoustic imaging (PAI). There are few publications demonstrating already the benefits of combining PTT with other therapeutic modalities such as photoacoustic imaging in order to visualize tumor area and improve the diagnosis and therapeutic outcome monitoring [41,42].

In this work, two unique morphologies of TiN - nanobars and nanospheres have been synthesized to study, for the first time, the effect of TiN morphology on theranostic efficiency. *In vitro* anticancer but also, for the first time, antibacterial therapy was evaluated by using extremely

low power density 380 mW/cm² in NIR light (940 nm). Comparing the TiN morphologies, higher anticancer PTT effect in Hela cells was achieved in TiN nanobars while TiN nanospheres showed better antibacterial efficiency in both bacterial strains (Fig. 1). The mechanism behind that was in the case of cancer cells studied by optical and TEM microscopy of labelled cells and ICPMS, showing significantly higher concentration of TiN nanobars in direct contact on the membrane or inside the Hela cells compared to TiN nanospheres. In bacteria, however, TiN nanospheres were more PTT efficient. As it is known, the size of bacterial cells is smaller than mammalian cells and cell wall structure in bacteria is different compared to somatic cells, thus the nanoparticles are not entering the bacteria [43]. Therefore, PTT effect of both TiN NPs is caused from the outside of the bacteria and as it is known from the literature that spherical particles have better affinity towards bacteria cell wall compared to rod like particles. Therefore, PTT effect of TiN spheres is higher than in TiN bars [44,45]. Nevertheless, in both cases such mild irradiation conditions in NIR using less harmful source of the light (380 mW/cm²) than conventional PTT treatments (800 nm laser light) is definitely beneficial for the body, protecting the surrounding healthy tissue. Moreover, pilot *in vivo* experiment shows promising EPR (Enhanced Permeability and Retention) effect of both TiN nanocrystals with strong PA signal in NIR region, enabling deep tissue imaging of the desired organs.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Synthesis and characterization of TiN nanostructures - nanobars and nanospheres

First, TiO₂ nanowires and nanospheres were synthesized (250 mg) and then converted to TiN nanobars and nanospheres by nitridation at high temperature using our previously reported protocol [46]. A more detailed description of TiO₂ and then TiN syntheses is described in Supporting Information (Methods S1-S4).

2.2. Photothermal efficiency of TiN nanostructures

To study the photothermal effect, 35 µg/mL aqueous solution of TiN nanostructures (1 mL) were irradiated by a NIR LED light (940 nm, 318 mW/cm², Solis® high-power LEDs from Thor Lab) from a fixed distance. The cuvette was placed in such a way that all the solution directly faced the light source. The temperature of the solutions was monitored at certain time interval by a digital thermometer with a type K thermocouple (RS PRO, 0.075 mm diameter) submerged in the solution. The cuvette was tightly sealed with its lid before starting irradiation.

Fig. 1. The scheme of *in vitro* anticancer and antibacterial PTT efficiency of TiN nanobars and nanospheres using NIR light (940 nm) based on their morphology.

2.3. *In vitro* experiments

2.3.1. *In vitro* – cell cultures

For *in vitro* toxicity studies, human cervical carcinoma HeLa (ATCC) and human monocyte-like THP-1 (ECCOCC) cell lines were used. Both cell lines were cultivated at 37 °C under a 5% CO₂ atmosphere in DMEM – Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (Sigma-Aldrich) for HeLa and RPMI-1640 medium (Sigma-Aldrich) for THP-1, both supplemented with 1% L-Glutamine, 10% FBS, and 1% PenStrep (10,000 U penicillin, 10 mg streptomycin/ml⁻¹).

2.3.2. Microscopy imaging of TiN labeled cells

2.3.2.1. Optical microscopy. Cells were seeded in the 24-well plate in density of 50×10^3 and let them 24 hours to adhere on the plastic chambers. After 24h, samples of TiN nanobars and nanospheres were added into the cells in the final concentration of 50 µg/mL. After 24 h incubation of TiN nanocrystals with cells, cells were washed several times with PBS and imaged by using optical microscopy (microscope Olympus IX 70).

2.3.2.2. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Samples were fixed with 2.5% glutaraldehyde in Sörrensen buffer (SB) for 1 h at room temperature and 1 h at 4 °C, washed with pure SB, treated with 1% OsO₄ solution in SB for 2h, and washed again, firstly with SB and consequently with MilliQ water. Dehydration was performed in a series of acetone/MilliQ water mixtures ending with dried acetone. Epoxy resin infiltration was done in resin/acetone solutions with decreasing acetone concentration and finally with pure epoxy resin mixture. Polymerization proceeded at 60 °C for 72 h.

Polymerized samples were cut into ultrathin sections (90 nm) LEICA EM UltraCut7, placed on formvar-coated copper slots (1 × 2 mm) and imaged in Jeol JEM 1400 Flash transmission electron microscope (TEM) at 80 kV acceleration voltage, using bootm-mounted FLASH 2kx2k CMOS camera.

2.3.3. *In vitro* PTT – cell viability

To test the TiN nanocrystals biocompatibility without the irradiation, HeLa and THP1 cells were seeded in 96-well plates (1×10^4 cells/well). Next day, the supernatant was discarded and fresh culture medium with various concentrations of TiN nanospheres (S) or nanobars (B) (0 – 100 µg/mL) were added for 24 h of treatment. After incubation, the biocompatibility was determined using LIVE/DEAD™ Viability/Cytotoxicity Kit for mammalian cells (Thermo Fisher) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, supernatant was collected, cells were washed with warm PBS (0.1 M, pH 7.4, Sigma-Aldrich), detached using Trypsin (0.25% in EDTA, Sigma-Aldrich), collected with fresh culture media containing the desired concentrations of fluorescent probes from the kit (1 µg/mL for Propidium Iodide (PI) and 50 µM of calcein-AM) and incubated for 20 min in the dark. Finally, fluorescent signal was measured with flow cytometer BD FACSVerser flow cytometer (Becton Dickinson). To check the *in vitro* PTT effect of TiN nanocrystals, HeLa cells were seeded in 24-well plates at a density of 1×10^5 cells per well and incubated for 24 h in DMEM medium supplemented with 10% FBS in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere at 37 °C. Next day, various concentrations (0, 10, 25, 50 and 100 µg/mL) of TiN nanospheres (S) and nanobars (B) were added to the cell cultures followed by 24 h treatment. Then, the cells were washed twice with PBS irradiated with 940 nm LED (SOLIS-940C, Thorlabs, Inc.) for 10 min at a power density of 380 mW/cm². Immediately after irradiation we checked the actual temperature using thermometer with a type K thermocouple (RS PRO, 0.075 mm diameter). The cells were then incubated for another 24 h. The cell viability was then recorded by flow cytometry using LIVE/DEAD™ Viability/Cytotoxicity Kit for mammalian cells (ThermoFisher), as described above. For all the cell viability assays, three independent experiments

were performed, each done in triplicate.

2.3.4. *In vitro* - PTT antibacterial therapy

Standard reference strains *Staphylococcus aureus* CCM 4223 (=ATCC 29213) and *Escherichia coli* CCM 3954 (=ATCC 25922) from the Czech Collection of Microorganisms (CCM, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University Brno, Czech Republic) were used.

The antibacterial activity was evaluated by the modification of EUCAST (European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing) standard microdilution method for the determination of MIC (minimum inhibitory concentration) and MBC (minimum bactericidal concentration). Tested substances of TiN nanocrystals were diluted in MH medium (cation adjusted Mueller-Hinton broth, BioRad, France) to obtain a concentration 12.5, 25, 50, 200 and 400 µg/mL in the well of microtiter plate. The plates were inoculated with a standard amount of the tested microbe - the initial density of the inoculum was equal to 5×10^5 CFU/mL. The suspension of bacteria with TiN nanocrystals were irradiated using a high-power LED (940 nm, 10 min, 380 mW/cm²) immediately after the 2 h cultivation period with TiN nanocrystals (in the presence of TiN in solution). Unlike the *in vitro* cell experiments, TiN nanocrystals were left in culture with bacteria during irradiation due to the difficult process of removing the particles from the bacteria especially due to the short incubation time and the different ordering of the experimental procedure. The irradiated plates were incubated for 18 ± 2 h at 35 ± 1 °C, and MICs were determined as the lowest concentration of tested compound that visibly inhibited bacterial growth. The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) is characterized as the minimum concentration of the sample required to achieve irreversible inhibition, *i. e.*, killing the bacterium after a period of incubation. To determine MBCs, the contents of the wells with visibly inhibited growth were inoculated onto MH agar (Trios, Czech Republic) – 10 µL for each well – and incubated for an additional 18 ± 2 h at 35 ± 1 °C. Negative growth of microbial colonies on agar determined bactericidal effect.

Moreover, in addition to determining MIC and MBC, the number of CFU/ml (=colony forming units) of live bacteria immediately after irradiation was determined and compared to the untreated control. The procedure was identical to the MIC determination. Immediately after irradiation, 10 µL of each well was further processed, diluted by saline and inoculated onto MH agar. After incubation at 35 ± 1 °C for 18 ± 2 h, grown bacterial colonies were counted and converted to the number of CFU/mL. The limit of detection was log2. All tests were performed in duplicate.

2.4. Photoacoustic imaging

Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments were performed using a VEVO 3100/LAZR-X multimodal imaging platform (FUJIFILM VisualSonics, Inc., Toronto, Canada). Photoacoustic spectra were acquired using a MX400 high-frequency ultrasound transducer (30 MHz, 50 µm axial, 110 µm lateral resolution; FUJIFILM VisualSonics, Inc., Toronto Canada) equipped with an original jacket for insertion of a 14 mm optical fiber for laser light delivery.

2.4.1. Phantom experiment

Prior to measurement, all samples were redispersed using a vortex mixer for 10 s and then sonicated for 5 min using DSA50-GL2–2.5L ultrasonic bath at a frequency of 40 kHz. After redispersion, each suspension was diluted to 4 concentrations (32 µg/mL, 63 µg/mL, 125 µg/mL, 250 µg/mL). Individual samples were vortexed again and transferred to 0.5 mm internal diameter silicone tubes. The tubes were then placed into a holder and the space around the tubes was filled with deionized water. Photoacoustic spectra were measured in two wavelength ranges, 680 – 970 nm, and 1200 – 2000 nm with 5 nm increments. Each tube was measured three times in both laser ranges and the values obtained were averaged and processed.

2.4.2. In vivo experiment

Center for Advanced Preclinical Imaging, First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University (CAPI) holds all necessary approvals for experimental animal work, GMO, open and closed sources of ionizing radiation. Four mice (C57Bl6 albino strain) were used in the experiment. Prior to TiN nanocrystal application, the mice were heated with an infrared lamp to increase vasodilation for easier intravenous (IV) application. Then, a solution containing $10 \mu\text{g}_{\text{nanocrystals}}/\text{g}_{\text{mouse}}$ diluted in $180 \mu\text{L}$ of PBS was injected intravenously via the tail vein. The mice were placed on a heated bed and ECG electrodes were attached for life monitoring (ECG and respiration). Mice were scanned before nanocrystal application, and then 1, 4, 24, 48, 72, and 168 h after application. The transducer imaging range was set from 6 to 18 mm, up to 20 mm in the case of tumor. B-mode gain was set to 19 dB, PA gain to 40 dB. Four mice (strain C57Bl6 albino) were used in the experiment. Before TiN nanocrystals application, mice were heated with an infrared lamp to increase vasodilation for easier intravenous application. Then, solution containing $10 \mu\text{g}$ nanocrystals/g mouse diluted in $180 \mu\text{L}$ of PBS was injected intravenously via the mouse tail vein. Mice were placed on a heated bed and ECG electrodes were connected for life monitoring (ECG and respiration). Mice were scanned before nanocrystals application, then 1, 4, 24, 48, 72, and 168 h after application. Transducer imaging range was set from 6 to 18 mm, in the case of tumor up to 20 mm. B-mode gain was set to 19 dB, PA gain to 40 dB. Wavelengths for PA 3D single mode were 830 nm in NIR-I range, resp. 1220 nm in NIR-II range. To evaluate nanoparticle biodistribution, the signal was investigated in the liver, spleen, left kidney and tumor. The data (organ volumetry) were evaluated using the VEVO Lab software. The wavelengths for PA 3D single mode were 830 nm in the NIR-I and 1220 nm in the NIR-II. To evaluate the biodistribution of the nanoparticles, the signal was examined in the liver, spleen, left kidney and tumor. The data (organ volumetry) were evaluated using the VEVO Lab software.

2.4.3. Data postprocessing and statistical analysis

Volumetric analysis of each organ of interest was performed by drawing an organ boundary for every fifth frame of the 3D acquisition. Then, PA Avr 3D values representing the PA signal intensity in each organ/tumor volume were plotted (Origin Pro 8 software, OriginLAB Corporation, Northampton, MA, USA) for each organ separately in time.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis and characterization of TiN nanobars and nanospheres

Two different TiN morphologies, namely nanobars and nanospheres, were achieved by pseudomorphic conversion of TiO_2 nanowires and nanospheres, respectively, via nitridation at 800°C for 5 h [46]. Fig. 2a and b shows the SEM images for TiO_2 nanowires and TiN nanobars, while the corresponding TEM images are provided in Fig. 2c and d. TiN nanobars have an average length, width and height of 1200, 220, and 40 nm, respectively (Fig. S1) [46]. Next, the microscopic characterization of TiO_2 and TiN nanospheres is reported in Fig. 2e–h. Morphological inspection confirmed that the TiN nanostructures maintain their structural feature as compared to respective parent TiO_2 morphologies during pseudomorphic conversion reaction. The presence of nanoholes on the TiN nanobars surface appeared due to the high temperature anion exchange and phase transition process in the presence of hot ammonia [46]. In contrast, TiN nanospheres consist of complex superstructures where ultrathin nanoridges decorated on a spherical structure with an average diameter of 200 nm [46]. An elemental mapping method employing field emission scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (FE-SEM-EDX) was employed to further characterize morphological and compositional properties of TiN nanobars. Fig. 2i highlights that in TiN nanobars both nitrogen (N) and oxygen (O) elements are homogeneously distributed within the nanoparticle. High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) micrographs (Fig. 2j) of TiN nanobars surface evidenced the

Fig. 2. SEM image of (a) TiO_2 nanowires and (b) TiN nanobars. Corresponding large area TEM micrographs of (c) TiO_2 nanowires and (d) TiN nanobars. Similarly, SEM images of (e) TiO_2 nanospheres and (f) TiN nanospheres. TEM images of (g) TiO_2 nanospheres and (h) TiN nanospheres. (i) FE-SEM-EDX elemental mapping for Ti, N, O of two overlapping TiN nanobars. (j) HRTEM with d-spacing showing the TiN nanobar surface and structure.

presence of an ultrathin amorphous oxide layer composed of titanium oxynitride (TiON) and titanium oxide (TiO₂) species due to the surface passivation [46].

X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (XPS, Fig. 3a and b) confirmed the presence of Ti-N and Ti-O bonds on TiN nanobars surface. Calculation of surface layer composition in TiN nanobars is summarized in Table S1. These oxide/oxy-nitride species are formed on the TiN nanostructures upon exposure to air but they do not affect the bulk composition and optical property [46]. Importantly, XRD patterns of the as-synthesized TiN nanobars and nanospheres (Fig. 3c) show the formation of highly crystalline cubic crystal structure of TiN as the only crystal phase. Nearly the same nature of XRD patterns confirms that the crystal structure of both TiN nanobars and nanospheres is very similar without any impurities or significant defects. Aqueous dispersions of TiN nanostructures were blue in color due to their broad optical absorption spanning the ultraviolet (UV), NIR-I (750 – 1000 nm), and NIR-II (1000 – 1350 nm) regions (Fig. 3d) as a consequence of their several plasmonic resonances [46]. Our very pure TiN nanocrystals are suitable for further PTT testing not only in their unique morphologies but also in their stability. Recently published works on TiN nanoparticles for PTT reported that TiN nanoparticles have been surface functionalized either during the synthesis by SiO₂ [47] or after by PEGylation [48], to prevent aggregation of bare TiN which is usually caused during high temperature nitridation or after synthesis. Our synthesized TiO₂ precursors, however, predict and keep the morphology of the produced final TiN as bars and spheres without sign of any aggregation. As measured by dynamic light scattering (DLS),

the TiN nanospheres in aqueous solution showed the hydrodynamic sizes of 140.9 ± 10.3 nm and 391.2 ± 28.0 nm confirming two fractions sizes of the present particles. These results are in a good accordance with the results obtained from SEM and TEM characterizations (Fig. 2 f and h). TiN nanobars in aqueous solution showed that there are two diameters – corresponding to width of 148.4 ± 26.8 nm and length of 996.7 ± 339.7 nm, which is in good agreement with the SEM images (Fig. S1). For the stability testing (Methods S5), we further investigated the ζ potentials in PBS dispersion. The ζ potential of the TiN nanobars immediately after the preparation was equal to -29.4 ± 1.4 mV. This value tickles the “magical” value of 30 mV in absolute value, which is the threshold of stability of the system [49]. The value of ζ potential was stable even after 2 h. A change in ζ potential came after ca. 5 h, when it dropped to -21.3 ± 1.2 mV. In the case of the TiN nanobars in PBS, the ζ potential was -31.1 ± 0.6 mV and after 5 h dropped to -21.0 mV. In both cases our TiN nanobars and nanospheres show highly stable system for further *in vivo* application.

3.2. Photothermal properties of prepared TiN

To explore the potential of TiN nanostructures as PTT agents, the photothermal properties of these nanostructures under NIR LED irradiation were evaluated. Aqueous solutions containing 35 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration of TiN nanobars and nanospheres were irradiated by a 940 nm LED light (318 mW/cm^2) from a fixed distance, and the solution temperature was collected at different time intervals. Fig. 4a and d show

Fig. 3. HR-XPS spectra of (a) Ti 2p and (b) N 1p regions for TiN nanobars. (c) XRD patterns for both TiN nanostructures and TiN standard. (d) Normalized UV-vis-NIR absorption spectra of TiO₂ and TiN nanostructures in DI-water.

Fig. 4. Photothermal heating curves from 35 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ aqueous solution of (a) TiN nanobars and (d) nanospheres. Heating and cooling curve of (b) TiN nanobars and (e) nanospheres. Corresponding calculation of the photothermal conversion efficiency for (c) TiN nanobars and (f) nanospheres. (g) UV-vis-NIR absorption spectra of 35 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ TiN nanostructures in DI-water. (h) Photothermal stability curves for TiN nanospheres.

that even using a low concentration (35 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), the temperature of the both TiN nanobars and nanospheres solution can reach a maximum of 31.4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ after 12 ~ 14 min of irradiation. It is important to note that the maximum temperature of 26.8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ was observed in pure water under 14 min of irradiation, which clearly indicates that the presence of TiN nanostructures can efficiently and rapidly convert NIR light energy into heat due to their superior plasmonic property. The temperature variation curve during the heating/cooling process was achieved by switching on/off the LED light for TiN nanobars (Fig. 4b) and nanospheres (Fig. 4e). Calculated photothermal conversion efficiency (η) of TiN nanobars and nanospheres are 20.2% (Fig. 4c) and 18.1% (Fig. 4f) respectively under 940 nm LED light irradiation. Details of photothermal efficiency calculation are described in the Supporting Information section Materials and methods S8. According to literature reports, obtained values of η reached as high as 48.6% for Ti_2N nanosheets at 808 nm [50], 52.6% for PVP-TiN nanodots at 1064 nm [51], 30.6% for Ti_3C_2 nanosheets at 808 nm [52], 61.5% for TiN nanosheets at 808 nm [53], but we have similar values as in the studies [48] (21.7% for TiN nanoparticles at 980 nm), and [54] (22.7% for TiN nanoparticles at 1064 nm). Fig. 4g compares the UV-vis-NIR absorption spectra of 35 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ TiN nanostructures solution in DI-water. The photothermal stability of the TiN nanospheres was also evaluated for three light on/off cycles using 940 nm LED light (380 mW/cm^2) for 14 min, and were left naturally cooling to room temperature after light off, while the

temperature was monitored. As shown in Fig. 4h, the photothermal properties of TiN nanospheres do not show any significant deterioration during these three irradiation cycles, which reveals that these structures possess good photothermal stability and can be utilized as a durable PTT agent.

3.3. *In vitro* PTT therapy on cells

3.3.1. *In vitro* experiments

We were curious if such mild conditions for irradiation (380 mW/cm^2) and NIR light (940 nm) could cause efficient killing of cancer cells. First, the biocompatibility of TiN nanobars (B) and nanospheres (S) in HeLa cells was demonstrated as they did not cause any decrease in viability up to the highest tested concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The THP-1 cell line, a well-defined model for immune-competent cells [55,56] was also introduced to evaluate a potential immunotoxicity of the materials. Same result was achieved, as no decrease in viability of THP-1 cells was observed after 24 h of incubation up to 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of TiN nanobars or nanospheres (Fig. S2).

To test the PTT capabilities of both TiN nanocrystals, the viability of identically incubated HeLa cells was determined after irradiation with 940 nm LED light (380 mW/cm^2) for 10 min. From the observed results shown in the Fig. 5a can be clearly seen that in both TiN morphologies, there is a significant decrease in cell viability when using a

Fig. 5. *In vitro* PTT on HeLa cells (a) cell viability, (b) temperature measured immediately after irradiation; Conditions: 940 nm NIR LED light, irradiation time: 10 min, max. power density: 380 mW/cm².

concentration of 50 µg/mL. TiN nanobars showed higher PTT effect since IC₅₀ (half-maximal inhibition concentration) was barely surpassed as compared with TiN nanospheres where the viability was still slightly above 70%. Importantly, irradiated control cells without TiN nanocrystals showed no decrease in viability (Fig. 5a) as well as non-irradiated cells with TiN nanocrystals (100 µg/mL) (Fig.S2). At the same time, we measured the temperature of the irradiated cells immediately after 10 min irradiation. With the increasing concentration of TiN NPs the temperature measured in the cell medium was also increasing in both TiN morphologies. When using 50 µg/mL concentration, the difference in the measured temperatures between the TiN nanobars and nanospheres was the most significant. Fig. 5b shows that in TiN nanobars labelled cells the temperature increased to 56.3 °C, while in the case of TiN nanospheres the temperature was lower 49.7 °C. In both cases, once the temperature exceeded 50 °C, the cells were completely destroyed by local heating (see Fig. 5b).

As it was shown in the Fig. 5, there is a significant difference in the cell viability after irradiation depending on the morphology of the TiN

nanocrystals. To find an explanation for such difference, we prepared the cells exactly the same as for the PTT *in vitro* experiments and with the labelling concentration of 50 µg/mL. Then we washed the cells with PBS, collected them and measured the concentration of Ti element in the cells via ICP-MS (Methods S6). From the observed results (see Fig. 6a) it was precisely estimated that in the case of TiN nanobars the Ti amount inside the HeLa cells or those TiN that are very strongly adhered on the cell membrane, even after washing the cells before irradiation, is more than double (227 pg/cell) than in the case of TiN nanospheres (95 pg/cell). This fact is also confirmed from optical images of labelled cells (Fig. 6b), where significantly more amount of TiN nanobars is visible on the surface of cells. TEM images of cells after 24 h of TiN incubation are depicted in the Fig. 6c. Both TiN bars as well as TiN spheres are located inside the cells, most probably in the endosomes in their early or late states [57]. Those endosomes containing TiN nanobars are much bigger and lighter than endosomes with TiN spheres however both types of TiN nanoclusters are localized inside these organelles and do not enter the nucleus.

From these observations showed above we can conclude that TiN nanobars are more efficient in PTT anticancer treatment because they are present in the direct area of cells (closely and strongly adhered on the cell membrane or in the process of endocytosis and also internalized in the endosomes inside the cells) in more than double quantity than TiN nanospheres. However, the most important is fact, that we were using the similar concentrations of TiN for efficient cancer killing like in other literature [47,48,58] but using much smaller power density of light which unambiguously show better plasmonic properties of our TiN nanocrystals compared to so far known literature.

Since we have observed that the TiN nanobars are uptaken or stay very strongly adsorbed on the membrane of the cells, one of the very important aspect is possible cytotoxic effect of these particles on human cells. The safety of human exposure still represents a significant challenge for any new designed nanosystem for biomedical applications. Particular emphasis should be placed on its potential long-term harmful effects. Furthermore, it was documented that the shape of the one-dimensional materials (nanotube/nanofibre/nanorod) might be responsible for their chronic toxicity leading to cell fibrosis (best described in the literature through carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [59]). Therefore, a long-term experiment involving repeatable exposure of both cell models to TiN nanocrystals was implemented to more accurately mimic the real-time application of the nanosystems (Methods S7). The experiment involved four treatments of 12.5 µg/mL of TiN nanospheres or nanobars at various time points, which resulted to the cumulative dose of 50 µg/mL after 14 days (a dose that showed significant anticancer effect following *in vitro* PTT therapy). Cell proliferation and morphology and additional three endpoints were assessed after 14 days to comprehensively investigate the biological response of tested cell modes to the TiN materials. No significant adverse effect was found in all the three tested endpoints involving cell viability, cell cycle profile and cell metabolic activity highlighting the exceptional biocompatible nature of TiN nanocrystals (Fig. S3). This result further strengthens the potential of these materials in biomedical applications.

3.3.2. Antibacterial PTT therapy

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study demonstrating *in vitro* photothermal therapy of TiN nanocrystals on bacteria. We performed comprehensive PTT experiments using both TiN nanospheres and nanobars on two bacterial strains, namely *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Both TiN nanocrystals showed extremely powerful antimicrobial effect (Table S2) and effectively caused bacterial inhibition (determination of minimum inhibitory concentration – MIC) after irradiation. More importantly, they destroyed the bacteria completely (determination of minimum bactericidal concentration – MBC). The MIC and MBC of TiN nanobars were determined at 50 µg/mL for both studied bacterial strains. Slightly better antibacterial activity was shown by TiN nanospheres, when the MIC and MBC were set at 25 µg/mL. Such low

Fig. 6. (a) Determination of the amount of Ti per cell by ICP-MS, (b) microscopy imaging of the HeLa cells; (left) control cells, (middle) TiN nanobar labeled cells and (right) TiN nanosphere labeled cells, and (c) TEM images of cells labelled by TiN bars (left) and spheres (right); all cells in (a), (b) and (c) were prepared in same conditions as for PTT *in vitro* experiment (after 24 h of incubation of HeLa cells with 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of TiN nanobars and TiN nanospheres and after washing with PBS). Scale bars in TEM correspond to 500 nm for the insets.

concentration of both type of TiN nanocrystals shows efficient antibacterial effect.

The prompt bactericidal effect of TiN nanocrystals therapy was also confirmed by different experiments in which the numbers of viable bacteria in CFU/mL were determined immediately after irradiation (Figs. 7 and S4).

The number of viable bacteria (CFU/mL) immediately after irradiation was dependent on the concentration of TiN nanocrystals in the suspension. TiN nanobars with 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ concentration, reduced the number of CFU/mL by 2 orders (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and 2.5 orders (*E. coli*) of magnitude as compared to the untreated control. At a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, a significant decrease in log CFU/mL of more than 4 orders of magnitude was determined.

TiN nanospheres at a concentration of 12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ slightly reduced the CFU/mL count by 1.5 order (*E. coli*) and 1 order (*Staphylococcus aureus*) of magnitude compared to the untreated control. It is highly exciting to notice that at a concentration of 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, a marked decrease in log CFU/mL more than 4 orders of magnitude was observed in both tested bacterial strains. This significant decrease in the number of viable bacteria confirmed the immediate bactericidal effect of PTT therapy and is consistent with the results of MIC and MBC.

TiN nanobars and nanospheres have no effect to bacterial strains without irradiation. Irradiation alone (without nanocrystals) has no effect on viability for both bacterial strains. As it is known from literature, the size of bacterial cells is smaller than mammalian cells and cell wall structure in bacteria is different compared to somatic cells, thus the

Fig. 7. The number of viable bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* immediately after irradiation at different concentrations of TiN nanobars and nanospheres. Notice: in 25 μg/mL of TiN nanospheres no *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria were viable, in 50 μg/mL TiN NPs no viable bacteria in both strains were observed.

nanoparticles are not easily entering the bacteria [43]. PTT effect of both TiN NPs in bacteria is caused just from the outside (surrounding medium). Our results agree well with the literature showing that spherical particles have better affinity towards bacteria cell wall compared to rod like particles and therefore PTT effect of TiN spheres is higher than in TiN bars [44,45].

3.4. Photoacoustic imaging

3.4.1. Phantom measurements

The photoacoustic imaging (PA) can provide real-time detection of an *in vivo* biological structure and functional information in a non-invasive and non-ionizing manner. Owing to their high photothermal-conversion performance, the TiN nanocrystals have shown a great potential for the use as contrast-enhanced PA nanoagents [48]. We searched for any signature of difference and dependence of the two types of morphologies (nanobars and nanospheres) on the PA signal *in vitro*. From the phantom experiments (Fig. 8), both TiN nanospheres and nanobars show increasing PA signal with increased concentrations in the entire NIR-I (680 – 970 nm) and also NIR-II. In the NIR-II wavelength range, signals were found between 1200 – 1300 nm (Figs. 8 and S5). This PA intensity signal at such high wavelength is highly beneficial and important enabling very deep tissue imaging.

3.4.2. *In vivo* photoacoustic imaging

Both prepared TiN nanocrystals represent a special class of plasmonic species with a large surface area and therefore they have excellent PA and PTT properties even in NIR wavelengths.

Fig. 8. PA intensities of different concentrations of TiN nanobars (left) and TiN nanospheres (right) measured at 830 nm (upper line) and at 1220 nm (bottom line). Images were acquired using following parameters: PA Gain 33 dB, 2D Gain 13 dB, Depth: 12 mm, Width 2.36 mm.

Fig. 9. (a) TiN nanospheres and (b) nanobars photoacoustic signal and imaging of the tumor (marked region), 24 h after intravenous administration. Notice: Images were acquired using the VEVO LAZR-X system in 3D multi-wavelength mode, with maximum energy settings at 710 nm, 790 nm, and 900 nm. The parameters were as follows: PA gain set to 40 dB, 2D gain set to 25 dB, imaging depth of 18 mm, imaging width of 15.36 mm, and a 3D step size of 0.102 mm.

From the pilot results of *in vivo* PA imaging the highest signal was observed in the liver, which is responsible for the hepatobiliary excretion route. Strong signal was also observed in the highly vascularized spleen. Negligible signal was detected in the kidney, indicating that the particles are not excreted via the renal route (data not shown).

In addition, a significantly higher signal was observed in the tumor compared to the surrounding tissue (Fig. 9). Nanoparticle entrapment in the tumor is probably caused by increased tumor angiogenesis and possibly by the EPR effect. Maximum signal in the tumor was observed between 24 and 48 hours after IV administration in the case of both TiN nanospheres and nanobars.

In the 21st century, there is an enormously urgent need to find and develop new effective strategies for cancer treatment as well as innovative methods for solving antibacterial resistance. As from World Health Organization (WHO)'s cancer agency, it was analyzed, that over 35 million new cancer cases are predicted in 2050, which means an incredible 77% increase from the estimated 20 million cases in 2022. On the other hand, bacterial infections become the second largest cause of death globally calling for urgent strengthening of mitigation strategies. TiN has emerged as a plasmonic, highly biocompatible, electrocatalytic and environmentally friendly material with unique physicochemical properties together with cost-effectiveness essential for wide utilization.

In this study, we aimed to show that two different TiN morphologies, nanobars and nanospheres could effectively kill cancer cells and two important bacteria strains as well via *in vitro* PTT therapy compared to other works in mild conditions (less power and NIR LED light), moreover enabling *in vivo* imaging of the TiN inside the body during the treatment.

In conclusion, we described *in vitro* PTT properties of plasmonic TiN nanostructures, prepared with two distinct morphologies - nanobars and nanospheres, which were studied not only on cancer Hela cells but for the first time also on bacteria. Due to excellent multiple plasmonic resonances and high stability, both TiN morphologies showed excellent NIR PTT efficiency even at very low power density LED light source using the similar concentrations of TiN as in all other recent studies where 808 nm laser of much higher power density was used. Long-term biocompatibility as well as *in vivo* EPR effect via photoacoustic imaging predict for both types of TiN nanocrystal morphologies promising future for anticancer and antibacterial PTT treatments.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Katerina Polakova: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Sourav Rej:** Writing – original

draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Sarka Hradilova:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jan Belza:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Tomas Malina:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Katerina Barton Tomankova:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Renata Vecerova:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Petr Matous:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Petr Paral:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Ariana Opletalova:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Jana Soukupova:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Tomas Pluhacek:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Ludek Sefc:** Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Radek Zboril:** Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Stepan Kment:** Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Alberto Naldoni:** Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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